

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF TOPICAL ETHOSOMAL GEL CONTAINING BIFONAZOLE FOR TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract

Bifonazole ethosomal gel was prepared by phospholipid (soya lecithin), ethanol and propylene glycol using hot method by incorporating ethosomal formulation into 1% w/v of carbopol gel which leads to ethosomal gel. Drug compatibility with excipients was checked by FT-IR and DSC studies. The prepared ethosomal gel was evaluated for pH, spreadability, viscosity, Drug entrapment efficacy and *in-vitro* drug release. Stability study of the formulation was done at room temperature for the period of 3 months. Drug-polymer compatibility studies showed no incompatibility between the drug and phospholipid. The F8 formulation showed more entrapment efficacy and highest *in vitro* drug release.

In- vitro permeation studies through egg membrane showed good drug release in the range of 65.41% to 93.43% over a period of 12 h. The best formulation was found to be F8 showing *in- vitro* drug release of 93.43%. The correlation and coefficient (R^2) values obtained from the kinetic equation shows the drug release from all the formulation (F1-F9) follow zero order and Higuchi drug release mechanism.

Keywords: Ethosomal gel, Bifonazole, Transdermal drug delivery, Phospholipid, Propylene glycol, Ethanol.

1.INTRODUCTION

The skin serves as a protective tissue, permeability barrier, and a barrier against foreign molecules from the outside environment. It is the largest organ of the body¹. Transdermal drug delivery systems serves better than oral delivery systems because they avoid gastrointestinal disruption and first-pass drug metabolism². The most impermeable barrier to drug penetration is skin, which limits the bioavailability of drugs administered topically. As a result, special drug carriers are needed to get pass the stratum corneum, the skin's natural barrier, and deliver drug molecules with a variety of physico-chemical properties to the systemic circulation.³ Ethosomes are "ethonolic liposomes" and can range in size from 30 nm to many microns. Ethosomes are non-invasive drug delivery systems that allow drug to penetrate deeply into the epidermal layers or the bloodstream.⁴ Ethosomes are soft, flexible vesicles designed for improved active drug delivery. Ethosomes are modified liposomes that have high ethanol content. Phospholipids (Phosphatidylcholine, Phosphatidylserine, and Phosphatidic Acid), a high concentration of alcohol (Ethanol and Isopropyl Alcohol), and water make up the ethosomal system⁵. Due to the high concentration of ethanol present in ethosomes, which disrupts the arrangement of the lipid bilayer in skin, this improves the ability of vesicles to penetrate the stratum corneum. Ethosomes can quickly penetrate the skin with drugs from BCS class 4 that have low solubility and permeability by employing ethosomal carriers.⁶ By employing gel and ethosomes assisted formulation, it is expected as promising carriers for transdermal delivery⁷. In this study, an ethosomal gel formulation containing Bifonazole is prepared in order to increase the dermal penetration and sustain drug delivery.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials: Bifonazole, Phosphatidylcholine, Carbopol 934 are obtained from Yarrow chem products, Mumbai, Ethanol is obtained from Changshu hongsheng fine chemicals, China, Propylene glycol, Methyl paraben, Propyl paraben and Triethanolamine are procured from Karnataka fine chem, Bangalore and all other solvents are of analytical grade.

2.2. Methods:

PREFORMULATION STUDIES:

2.2.1. Melting point: Melting point was determined by using digital melting point apparatus (Guna). Small amount of sample powder of Bifonazole was filled in glass capillary tube (previously sealed on one end). The capillary tube is placed into melting point apparatus. The temperature at which it starts melt was noted⁸.

2.2.2. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC): Thermal behavior of pure drug and pure drug = phospholipid was studied with the help of DSC by KBr pellet method.⁹

2.2.3. Solubility: Solubility of the Bifonazole was done by using methanol, ethanol, acetone, tween 80, 0.1N HCL buffer, HCL.¹⁰

2.2.4. Standard curve of Bifonazole: Preparation of standard stock solution

The Bifonazole standard reference stock solution was prepared by accurately weighed 10 mg of Bifonazole dissolved in a 100 ml of phosphate buffer 6.8 pH. Again 10 ml was withdrawn and diluted to 100 ml with phosphate buffer 6.8 pH. From this stock solution serial dilution were made to obtain the solution in concentration ranging from 1-12 µg/ml. They were analyzed spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance at 254 nm.¹¹

2.2.5. Drug excipients compatibility studies: Fourier transforms infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy

The infrared spectra of Bifonazole and other excipients was recorded using FT-IR spectrophotometer. The IR spectra of physical matrix were compared with that of Bifonazole to check for any possible drug- excipients interaction.¹²

3. FORMULATION OF BIFONAZOLE ETHOSOMAL GEL

3.1. Procedure:

For the preparation of phospholipid dispersion, phospholipid was dispersed in distilled water and heated using hot plate magnetic stirrer to 40 °C until a colloidal solution is obtained. Afterward, the ethonolic solution was prepared by dissolving Bifonazole in ethanol, propyleneglycol is added to it and heated to 40 °C. When both the mixture reaches 40 °C the ethonolic solution is added to phospholipid dispersion drop wise drop with constant stirring at 1500 rpm to form ethosomes. Then, the ethosomal solution was left to cool down at the room temperature. The ethosomes were separated from supernatant using centrifugation. The separated ethosomes were mixed with the 1% carbopol gel by base.¹³ The composition of all the formulations prepared is illustrated in table-1.

SI. NO	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
01	Bifonazole (mg)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
02	Phospholipid (mg)	300	300	300	600	600	600	900	900	900
03	Ethanol (ml)	6	9	12	6	9	12	6	9	12
04	Propylene glycol (ml)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
05	Distilled water (ml)	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30

Table 1: Formulation table of Ethosomes

3.2. Preparation of gel base:

1% w/v gel base was prepared by dispersing carbopol 934 in distilled water containing 0.2% methyl paraben and 0.02% propyl paraben using mechanical stirrer. The pH was then adjusted to neutral

using triethanolamine.¹³

4. Evaluation of ethosomal gel:

4.1. Physical properties:

The physical properties of the prepared ethosomal gel formulations were examined for color, homogeneity, consistency and phase separation.^{13,14}

4.2 Particle size distribution and Zeta potential:

Particle size and zeta potential can be determined by a zeta-sizer or dynamic light scattering (DLS) using a computerized inspection system and photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS). Ethosomes vary in size from tens of nanometers to microns, and their size is determined by the formulation's composition.^{14,15}

4.3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM): Visualization of ethosomes can be done using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). This provides visual information about the size, shape, surface morphology and lamellarity.¹⁶

4.4. pH determination: The pH of the gels was determined by digital pH meter. A solution of 1g of gel was made with 25 ml of distilled water. And the electrode was dipped into the gel solution for 30

min until the constant reading obtained and constant reading was noted. The measurement of pH of each formulation was replicated three times.¹⁷

4.5. Viscosity determination: The viscosity of the prepared ethosomal gel was determined using Brookfield viscometer (Brookfield LV, spindle no. 64). A glass container was filled with a ethosomal gel and the spindle of the viscometer was allowed to rotate at predetermined speeds (5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60 and 100 rpm). For each speed the viscosity was recorded.¹⁸

4.6. Determination of spreadability:

Spreadability was determined by placing 2 g of gel on one slide and the another slide tied with 200 g weight is kept on the top of the first slide, then it is allowed to spread for 1min and the length of the spreaded gel on the glass slide was measured using scale.

$$S=M.L/T$$

Where, S=Spreadability, M=Weight tied to upper slide, L=Length, T=Time¹⁹

4.7. Determination of entrapment efficacy

The formulation was centrifuged in centrifuge tube, the supernatant was collected and the amount of drug was determined by UV spectrophotometer at 254nm.

$$\% \text{Entrapment efficacy} = (T-C)/T \times 100$$

Where, T=Total amount of drug in the formulation, C=Amount of drug in supernatant²⁰

4.8. *In-vitro* release study

For the drug release investigations, Franz diffusion cells were employed. The egg membrane was uniformly covered with 1g of ethosomal gel. The donor and receptor chambers of the diffusion cell were clamped down on the egg membrane. To solubilize the medication, a freshly made PBS

solution (pH 6.8) was poured into the receptor chamber. A magnetic stirrer was used to stir the receptor chamber. Samples (1 ml aliquots) were taken at appropriate intervals. After the proper dilutions, samples were examined with a UV Visible spectrophotometer to determine their drug content. To find the amount of medication release at each time interval, cumulative drug release calculations were performed. The drug's cumulative release across the egg membrane was calculated as a function of time.

$$\% \text{Drug release} = \text{cumulative drug release} / \text{Drug dose} \times 100^{21,22}$$

4.9. Stability studies

Stability tests were carried out to verify if the formulation had any significant alterations while being stored. Every formulation was stored at room temperature for three months. The formulations' stability was assessed by measuring their pH, spreadability, viscosity, drug entrapment effectiveness, and in vitro drug release.^{23,24}

5. RESULTS

5.1. Pre formulation studies - Melting point:

Melting point of Bifonazole was determined using digital melting point apparatus. It was found to be 150.67 °C which was similar to reference standard.

5.2. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):

Thermal behavior of pure drug and pure drug + phospholipid was studied with the help of DSC. The thermograms obtained are shown in figure:2 and figure:3 respectively. Drug has shown sharp endothermic peak at 153.02°C. It is corresponding to the melting point of Bifonazole. The phospholipid shown sharp melting point near 159.66°C. Therefore, Bifonazole appeared in the physical mixture indicating that there was no possible interaction between the drug and the excipients in the ethosomal formulation.

Figure 1: Thermogram of pure drug

Figure 2: Thermogram of pure drug + phospholipid

5.3. Solubility: The solubility of Bifonazole is essentially constant. Bifonazole was freely soluble in methanol and ethanol.

5.4. Standard calibration plot of Bifonazole: The λ_{\max} of Bifonazole in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was found to be 254 nm. The absorbance values are tabulated in the table 4. Bifonazole obeyed Beer Lamberts law in the concentration range of 1-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Figure 3: Standard calibration curve of Bifonazole

5.5. Drug-excipients and drug-polymer compatibility studies: FT-IR spectroscopy

Drug polymer compatibility studies were carried out using Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy to establish any possible interaction of bifonazole with phospholipid used in the formulation. The FT-IR spectra of the formulation were compared with the FT-IR of the pure drug. The results indicated that the principle peaks obtained from the combination were almost similar to that of pure drug without any significant change in their position, indicating no chemical interaction between bifonazole (drug) and phospholipid (soya lecithin).

Figure 4: FT-IR characteristics peak of pure drug and excipients

Groups (cm ⁻¹)	Compound class	Bifonazole	Bifonazole +Phospholipid
C-H Bending (3100-2000)	Methylene	3030	3031
		2320	2320
C=N Stretching (1690-1400)	Nitriles	1496	1521
C-N Stretching (1500-1200)	Aromatic Nitro Compounds	1291	1274
C=O Stretching (1725-1700)	Carboxylic Acid	1730	1733
C=C Bending (1600-1400)	Alkenes	1455	1455

Table 2: Interpretation of FT-IR

5.6. Homogeneity

A visual test for homogeneity of drug product may be useful, at least for a exhibit batch, to ensure no separation of phase, no foreign matter, no synneresis, all batches of ethosomal gel containing bifonazole were smooth with a homogenous appearance.

Formulation code	Homogeneity
F1	+++
F2	+++
F3	+++
F4	+++
F5	+++
F6	+++
F7	+++
F8	+++
F9	+++

(+ poor, ++ average, +++ good, ++++excellent)

Table 3: Data for homogeneity

5.7. pH

The pH of all the formulated ethosomal gel exhibited uniformity in their values and were found to be between 5.4 ± 0.3 to 5.63 ± 0.1 indicating its compatibility which was shown in Table 4. Hence no dermal irritation was expected and ultimately achieved patient compliance.

5.8. Spreadability

The spreadability of all the formulations of ethosomal gel exhibited uniformity and was found to be between 15.66 ± 0.5 cm to 16.88 ± 0.3 cm indicating its results in Table 4. Hence, increase in the spreadability may lead to more absorption.

5.9. Viscosity

The viscosity of the formulated ethosomal gel was between 33902 ± 1429 cps to 35301 ± 422 cps and the results were shown in Table 4. If viscosity increases it leads to more drug absorption and thereby it increases instilled time and drug loss can be minimized.

5.10. Drug entrapment efficacy

The drug entrapment efficacy was carried out for all the formulations. It was found between 84.3 ± 0.4 %. The F8 formulation shows high entrapment efficacy due to the presence of high concentration of phospholipid.

Formulation Code (n=3±SD)	Viscosity in cps	Spread ability in cm	pH	Drug entrapment Efficacy in %
F1	35000±282	16.88±0.3	5.4±0.3	39.55±0.3
F2	34415±714	15.66±0.5	5.56±0.1	44.15±0.3
F3	34057±1351	16.77±0.1	5.5±0.1	41.7±0.4
F4	35100±140	16.22±0.1	5.53±0.1	58.95±0.07
F5	33902±1429	16.55±0.1	5.56±0.2	61.05±0.2
F6	34451±1907	16.35±0.03	5.5±0.2	58.05±0.4
F7	34300±2687	16.44±0.1	5.43±0.3	76.95±0.3
F8	35301±422	16.55±0.1	5.63±0.1	84.3±0.4
F9	34800±1979	16.33±0.1	5.53±0.3	74.05±0.4

Table 5: Data for pH, Spreadability, Viscosity, Drug entrapment efficacy

5.11. SEM Analysis

The ethosomes were found to be in spherical shape.

Figure 5: SEM analysis of ethosomes

5.12. Zeta potential and particle size

The magnitude of zeta potential an indication of the potential stability of the colloidal system. If all the vesicles have a large negative and positive zeta potent, they will repel each other and they show dispersion stability. The zeta potential of best formulation was found to be -0.279 mV. Which indicate that the produced ethosomes were stable with no agglomeration. The particle size of ethosome was found in the range of 682.2 nm.

Figure 6: Zeta potential

Figure 7: Particle size distribution

5.13. In-vitro drug release studies:

All the formulated ethosomal gel was evaluated to determine *in-vitro* drug release according to the procedure described in methodology. Formulation F8 showed more drug release, so F8 was selected as best formulations for the better therapeutic action.

The results are shown in table 6.

Time in hrs	Percentage cumulative drug release (%)								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	8±0.5	8.25±0.7	7.66±0.4	10.25±0.4	9.25±0.3	8.58±0.6	16.66±0.8	11±0.3	16.66±0.6
2	13.91±0.3	13.33±0.6	13.15±0.6	16.45±0.6	16.43±0.4	15.58±0.5	23.75±0.5	17.97±0.5	23.75±0.7
3	17.01±0.4	17.08±0.3	16.49±0.5	22.78±0.5	21.84±0.5	19.81±0.6	25.80±0.8	27.65±0.4	25.80±0.5
4	22.93±0.6	20.01±1.7	24.48±0.4	26.80±0.4	25.85±0.6	25.7±0.6	31.88±0.5	35.45±0.3	31.88±0.6
5	28.87±0.7	24.31±0.6	31.21±0.7	34.65±0.4	31.76±0.5	31.03±0.5	36.24±0.4	43.38±0.5	36.24±0.7
6	35.26±0.5	27.02±0.5	34.81±0.5	36.48±0.6	40.95±0.7	35.20±0.6	42.68±0.3	48.38±0.7	42.68±0.6
7	43.76±0.7	36.11±0.6	41.63±0.7	43.42±0.3	44.98±0.5	39.70±0.4	46.06±0.3	56.21±0.4	46.06±0.6
8	48.51±0.6	43.54±0.5	49.50±0.6	49.07±0.4	52.74±0.5	44.94±0.7	57.67±0.3	63.77±0.8	57.67±0.4
9	53.08±0.7	51.61±0.7	54.01±0.4	52.72±0.6	58.22±0.6	50.44±0.6	64.65±0.4	77.12±0.5	64.65±0.4
10	55.64±0.7	57.48±1.5	57.09±0.5	56.94±0.8	63.05±0.1	54.95±0.8	73.17±0.3	82.04±0.4	72.09±0.6
11	60.82±0.6	62.88±0.6	64.38±0.6	63.05±0.3	68.94±0.7	60.78±0.8	82.84±0.4	86.37±0.7	75.48±0.4
12	65.41±0.7	69.52±0.8	66.96±0.6	70.68±0.3	74.93±0.1	72.29±0.6	85.34±0.5	93.43±0.3	83.42±0.3

Table 6: Data for Percentage cumulative drug release of F1-F9

Figure 8: Cumulative % Drug Release of F7-F9

5.14. KINETIC MODEL OF BIFONAZOLE ETHOSOMAL GEL

The drug diffusion profiles of all the formulation were fitted into kinetic models such as Zero order, Higuchi model equation. From the results it was evident that all the formulations were more linear towards Zero order and Higuchi models with R^2 value ranging from 0.980-0.997 and 0.955-0.995 respectively indicating the drug release mechanism is by diffusion as given in the table 7.

Figure 9: Zero order plot for F7-F9

Figure 10: First order plot for F7-F9

Figure 11: Higuchi plot for F7-F9

Figure 12: Peppas's plot for F7-F9

Formulation code	Kinetic model					Best fit model
	Zero order (R ²)	First order (R ²)	Higuchi (R ²)	Peppas (R ²)	N value	
F1	0.991	0.989	0.977	0.731	0.11	Zero order
F2	0.980	0.938	0.984	0.766	0.111	Higuchi
F3	0.994	0.938	0.955	0.741	0.411	Zero order
F4	0.995	0.969	0.992	0.674	0.103	Zero order
F5	0.997	0.971	0.996	0.708	0.109	Zero order
F6	0.991	0.935	0.991	0.706	0.106	Zero and Higuchi
F7	0.982	0.897	0.982	0.638	0.103	Zero and Higuchi
F8	0.995	0.908	0.995	0.693	0.114	Zero and Higuchi
F9	0.987	0.925	0.984	0.628	0.101	Zero order

Table 7: Different kinetic model of Ethosomal gel of Bifonazole

5.15. Stability studies:

The formulation was kept for 3 months and checked for its pH determination, spreadability, viscosity and *in-vitro* drug release for 12 hours. The results have showed negligible changes in the parameters of F8 after 3 months of storage was given in table-8 and 9 respectively.

EVALUATION	RESULTS
pH determination	5.43±0.1
Spreadability	16.31±0.1
Viscosity	3523±3
Drug content	91.3%

Table 8: Data for stability study

Time in hrs	% Drug release of F8
1	10.56±0.03
2	16.96±0.45
3	26.64±0.51
4	34.44±0.44
5	44.39±0.54
6	47.37±0.61
7	55.25±0.56
8	62.79±0.51
9	76.19±0.32
10	81.01±0.43
11	85.39±0.33
12	92.61±0.37

Table 9: Stability study data of *In-vitro* drug of formulation

F8

6. CONCLUSION:

Based on the observations of the present study, it can be concluded that F8 formulation with combination of 9 ml ethanol and 900 mg of phospholipid (soya lecithin) used for the preparation of Ethosomal gel containing Bifonazole by Hot method shows a good results in all the evaluation parameters. The study revealed that the ethosomal formulation has been considered as a possible vesicular carrier for transdermal drug delivery system using BCS class-4 drugs.

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